

Substrate RF Non-Linear Characterization and Modeling

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Outline

Introduction / Context / Motivation

- Why linearity?
- Substrates for RF

Physics of RF substrates

- Charge Balance
- Trap Passivation
- Dynamic Effects (finite time constants)

Modelling (CPW lines)

- Instantaneous substrate impedance
- Correlation to measurements

Modelling of arbitrary layouts

- Approach and initial results

TCAD + T-line theory

TCAD + EM simulations

Introduction / Context / Motivation

- **Non-linearity Recap**
- **Substrate Requirements at RF**

Signal Distortion / System Linearity

Antenna

Non-linearity = spectral “smearing”.

⇒ adjacent band spectral contamination

⇒ Ever more stringent **linearity** specifications for FEMs

Network	Linearity IIP3 [dBm]
2G	55
3G	65
4G LTE	72
4G LTE + CA	Up to 90

Linearity Requirements by Network Standard

Substrate Requirements for RF

Substrate FoMs:

- Losses / coupling / ρ_{eff}
(TCAD+EM non-uniform material stack)
- Linearity / HD → talk's focus

Ideal linear transfer function: $y = f(x) = a \cdot x$
 Real non-linear transfer function: $y = f(x) = a \cdot x + b \cdot x^2 + c \cdot x^3 + \dots$

Example of substrate impact:

Substrate Requirements for RF

Standard-Si vs. High-Res. vs. Trap-Rich

Substrate FoMs:

- Losses / coupling / ρ_{eff}
(TCAD+EM non-uniform material stack)

Ideal linear transfer function: $y = f(x) = a \cdot x$
 Real non-linear transfer function: $y = f(x) = a \cdot x + b \cdot x^2 + c \cdot x^3 + \dots$

Linearity / HD

Semiconductors are non-linear by nature (field-effect).

Linearity depends on what the conditions are (n and p) at the interface.
 \Rightarrow TR is an *interface passivation* scheme.

Substrate Requirements for RF

EM + TCAD can be combined to simulate a range of RF passives on highly non-uniform Si-based substrates.

⇒ **Small-signal modelling OK!**

Substrate RF FoMs plotted vs bias

Answer: Yes !

→ Model of in this presentation validated over many parameters.

Full References:

- *Modeling of Semiconductor Substrates for RF Applications: Part I - Static and Dynamic Physics of Carriers and Traps*, doi: 10.1109/TED.2021.3096777.
- *Modeling of Semiconductor Substrates for RF Applications: Part II - Parameter Impact on Harmonic Distortion*, doi: 10.1109/TED.2021.3096781.

- Amplitude RF
- Point DC
- Fixed interface charge
- Interface traps and *trap-rich* passivation
- Dimensions of CPW
- Frequency
- Temperature

Motivation and Objectives of a Large-Signal Substrate Model

- Can we predict HD of a given material stack?
- How to model, taking into account all semiconductor effects
- Gain physical insight into parameter impact (future substrate developments, IC design, etc.)

Physics of RF Substrates

- Quantitative Analysis and Understanding
- Fundamentals of Interface Trap Passivation
- Dynamic effects (finite time constants)

Quantitative Charge Balance

How does Trap-Rich interface passivation work?

For Acceptor Traps: $Q_{\text{Empty}} = 0$
 $Q_{\text{Filled}} = -q$

For Donor Traps: $Q_{\text{Empty}} = +q$
 $Q_{\text{Filled}} = 0$

Traps in polysilicon:

$$g_{GA}(E) = NGA \cdot \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{EGA - E}{WGA}\right)^2\right\} \quad [\text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{eV}^{-1}] \quad (3.45)$$

$$g_{GD}(E) = NGD \cdot \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{EGD - E}{WGD}\right)^2\right\} \quad [\text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{eV}^{-1}] \quad (3.46)$$

$$g_{TA}(E) = NTA \cdot \exp\left\{\frac{E - E_C}{WTA}\right\} \quad [\text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{eV}^{-1}] \quad (3.47)$$

$$g_{TD}(E) = NTD \cdot \exp\left\{\frac{E_V - E}{WTD}\right\} \quad [\text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{eV}^{-1}] \quad (3.48)$$

Charge compensation: HR vs. TR

$$N_{free} = \int_0^{t_0} p(y) - n(y) dy \quad [\text{cm}^{-2}]$$

$$N_{trap} = \int_0^{t_0} N_{tD}^+(y) - N_{tA}^-(y) dy \quad [\text{cm}^{-2}]$$

$$N_{Applied}(V) = N_{ox} + C_{ox}(V - V_{MS}) \quad [\text{cm}^{-2}]$$

In all generality:

$$-N_{Applied} = N_{free} + N_{trap}$$

In a HR:

$$-N_{Applied} = N_{free}$$

In a « good » TR:

$$-N_{Applied} \approx N_{trap}$$

For any usual value of $N_{Applied}(V)$

Charge compensation: HR vs. TR

In a HR:

n and p vary strongly with the applied signal $V(t)$

In a « good » TR:

n and p remain very low for "any" signal $V(t)$

Concept of *Fermi-level pinning* \rightarrow **Quasistatic**

Charge compensation: HR vs. TR

Charges in the Semiconductor

- ■ ■ Donor Distr.
- ■ ■ Acceptor Distr.
- — — Fermi Level

Applied Charge

HR substrate

Large variations in n and p

⇒ Large variations in substrate impedance

⇒ Highly voltage-dependent (non-linear)

[Movie Animation Not Included in PDF Format]

*Quasistatic analysis
(DC or low-freq)*

Charge compensation: HR vs. TR

Charges in the Semiconductor

- ■ ■ Donor Distr.
- ■ ■ Acceptor Distr.
- - - Fermi Level

Applied Charge

TR substrate

Small variations in n and p

⇒ Small variations in
substrate impedance

⇒ Little voltage-
dependency
(at low freq. !!)

[Movie Animation Not Included in PDF Format]

*Quasistatic analysis
(DC or low-freq)*

At RF, full description
involves E_{QFn} , E_{QFp} ,
 $E_{QFtrap1}$, $E_{QFtrap2}$, etc.

For Large-Signal Substrate Modelling...

... interested in the behaviour of substrate impedance with the applied voltage signal.

$$Z_{NL}(V)$$

== Substrate impedance $Z_{sub}(V)$

Substrate impedance vs. voltage

== Substrate impedance $Z_{sub}(V)$

How does the substrate respond under large-signal excitation?

Can we use this $Z_{sub}(V)$ transfer function, for any signal $V(t)$?

Flip between these states in $\sim ns$??

Non-Equilibrium Dynamics

Voltage step applied to MOS device.

$$N_{ox} = 0 \text{ cm}^{-2}$$

$$V(t = 0^-) = -10 \text{ V}$$

Color map
 $n(x, y)$

$$V(t = +\infty) = +10 \text{ V}$$

Non-Equilibrium Dynamics

Voltage step applied to MOS device.

$$N_{ox} = 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-2}$$

$$V(t = 0^-) = -10 \text{ V}$$

Color map
 $n(x, y)$

$$V(t = +\infty) = +10 \text{ V}$$

Non-Equilibrium Dynamics Sinusoidal $V(t)$ - RF analysis

$$N_{freeINT} \triangleq \int_0^{1 \mu\text{m}} p(y) - n(y) dy \quad [\text{cm}^{-2}]$$

As f increases: only a spatial rearrangement of existing *available carriers through time*
 no (significant) generation/recombination

Non-Equilibrium Dynamics RF analysis

HD is maximum just after the end of the slow-wave mode f_{SW}

	ρ_{eff} [Ωcm]	f_{SW}
Standard Si	~ 10	5 - 15 GHz
HR with strong PSC	< 50	5 - 15 GHz
HR with weak PSC	50 - 200	1 - 5 GHz
TR	10k	10 - 50 MHz

In the slow-wave mode, the BOX impedance linearizes the overall substrate impedance.

Carrier inertia dampens impedance variations at high frequencies

Model to Measuremet Correlation

Non-Equilibrium Dynamics RF analysis

HD is maximum just after the end of the slow-wave mode f_{SW}

Observe these trends in measurements?

⇒ We set-up measurement benches at:
50 MHz, 250 MHz, 900 MHz, 2.5 GHz
 and **5.4 GHz**

(each setup uses dedicated filters and power amplifier)

Hardware Validation

Substrate impedance vs. voltage

— Measurements HR-SiO₂ $Q_{ox} = +8 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-2}$
 - · - Simulation

Substrate response in biased HR

Voltage Signal: **f = 900 MHz**
 A = 2.5 V
 DC = +15 V

Substrate impedance variation
gives rise to -35 dBm of H2
distortion

Substrate response in biased HR

Voltage Signal:
f = 900 MHz
A = 2.5 V
DC = -15 V

Larger impedance variation
gives rise to -12 dBm of H2
distortion

Substrate impedance vs. voltage

The substrate is always out of equilibrium in response to a large-signal $V_{RF}(t)$

The equilibrium $Z_{sub_{eq}}(V)$ curve's information is irrelevant !

Even more obvious for Trap-Rich (next slides)

Non-Equilibrium Dynamics

-Dynamics of traps

Don't let all previous slides mislead you into thinking that:

TR substrates are very linear, because ionized traps provide the compensation charge so that free carriers do not have to.

⇒ This statement is false !

To compensate for a change in applied charge $+\Delta Q$, there are four compensation mechanisms:

$n \nearrow$ Drift to/from other parts of
 $p \searrow$ the substrate

$N_{tA}^- \nearrow$ Requires capturing an electron

$N_{tD}^+ \searrow$ Requires capturing an electron
(equivalent to emitting a hole)

n and p must vary first.
 τ_{tn} and τ_{tp} are long, because n and p are low (TR)

Non-Equilibrium Dynamics

-Dynamics of traps

- · - Flat $Y_{eq}(V)$ curves: DC Fermi-level pinning
- Non-flat $Y_{neq}(V)$ curves: RF Fermi-level variations
Modulation of the available carriers

Instantaneous $Y_{neq}(V)$ curves do not follow the equilibrium $Y_{eq}(V)$ curves.

Further Model-Hardware Correlation

→ Model of in this presentation validated over many parameters:

- Amplitude
- DC bias
- Fixed interface charge
- Interface traps and *trap-rich* passivation
- Dimensions of CPW
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→ Model applied solely to CPW lines !

→ Could it be extended to arbitrary passive RF layouts ?

A detailed, multi-colored circuit board layout. The board is populated with various components and traces. The traces are primarily orange and red, forming a complex network. There are several circular components, possibly capacitors or inductors, and rectangular components, possibly integrated circuits. The board is divided into several sections by different colors and patterns, including green, blue, yellow, and purple. The overall appearance is that of a highly complex and dense electronic circuit.

Model Extension to Arbitrary Layout Structures

Arbitrary layout simulation - A proposed approach

Large-signal simulation methodology combining:

- a $2N$ -port EM simulation file S_{BEOL}
- an N -port EM simulation file S_{SUB}
- N non-linear dipole admittances $Y_{surf}(V)$

Sim. 1: Linear BEOL

BEOL EM Simulation

(a)

Material Stack A

(b)

BEOL EM Simulation.

(a) Layout representation and $2N$ port definitions.

(b) Material stack used for the BEOL EM layout simulation.

Sim. 2: Linear Si Substrate Regions

Substrate EM Simulation

Ports in "SUB-layer"

(a)

Material Stack B

(b)

Substrate EM Simulation.

(a) Layout representation and N port definitions.

(b) Material stack used for the Substrate EM layout simulation.

Initial validation of the approach

Under small-signal

Two-port crosstalk layout and representation of the EM ports ($N = 96$).

Simulated S_{21} of the two-port crosstalk structure of using 2 approaches:

1. A single EM simulation and six pins to excite the two GSG ports of the structure.
2. Combining two separate EM simulations employing respectively N ports and $2N$ ports, that are then reconnected together to model the entire layout and materials.

Practical implementation

Harmonic Balance

Large-signal simulation approach using ADS harmonic balance combining:

- Two EM S-parameter files (BEOL EM Simulation and Substrate EM Simulation)
- N non-linear surface admittance elements $Y_{surf}(V)$.

HARMONIC BALANCE

Var Eqn VAR
 Y_{surf_norm}
 $G_{surf_norm}(V)=G_{o0} + G_{o1}*V + G_{o2}*V^2 + G_{o3}*V^3 + G_{o4}*V^4$
 $C_{surf_norm}(V)=C_{o0} + (C_{o1})*V + C_{o2}*V^2 + C_{o3}*V^3 + C_{o4}*V^4$

SDD3P
 Y_{surf_1}
 $I[1,0]=(C_{surf_norm}(_v3)*f_0*(_v2)+(_v1)*G_{surf_norm}(_v3))*A1$
 $F[2,0]=_v2$
 $F[2,1]=_v1/f_0$
 $C[1]=$
 $Cport[1]=$

Var Eqn VAR
 $Area_1$
 $A1=50e-6*40e-6$

SDD3P
 Y_{surf_2}
 $I[1,0]=(C_{surf_norm}(_v3)*f_0*(_v2)+(_v1)*G_{surf_norm}(_v3))*A2$
 $F[2,0]=_v2$
 $F[2,1]=_v1/f_0$
 $C[1]=$
 $Cport[1]=$

Var Eqn VAR
 $Area_2$
 $A2=80e-6*40e-6$

SDD3P
 Y_{surf_3}
 $I[1,0]=(C_{surf_norm}(_v3)*f_0*(_v2)+(_v1)*G_{surf_norm}(_v3))*A3$
 $F[2,0]=_v2$
 $F[2,1]=_v1/f_0$
 $C[1]=$
 $Cport[1]=$

Var Eqn VAR
 $Area_3$
 $A3=50e-6*40e-6$

SDD3P
 Y_{surf_4}
 $I[1,0]=(C_{surf_norm}(_v3)*f_0*(_v2)+(_v1)*G_{surf_norm}(_v3))*A4$
 $F[2,0]=_v2$
 $F[2,1]=_v1/f_0$
 $C[1]=$
 $Cport[1]=$

Var Eqn VAR
 $Area_4$
 $A4=30e-6*40e-6$

Model on arbitrary layout: *2-port crosstalk structure*

Measured and simulated power of the output components of the **crosstalk structure** on samples **B28** and **B67** for a **900 MHz** input signal of power P_{in} . Low noise floor (-170 dBm) measurements courtesy of *Incize*.

Model on arbitrary layout: *2-port Meander Line*

Measured and simulated power of the output components of the **inductive meander line** on samples **B28** and **B67** for a **900 MHz** input signal of power P_{in} . Low noise floor (-170 dBm) measurements courtesy of *Incize*.

Model to hardware correlation

		CPW		Crosstalk		Meander	
		Meas.	Model	Meas.	Model	Meas.	Model
B28	$H1$	+14.6	+14.6	-33.2	-34.0	+13.5	+13.3
	$H2$	-82	-84	-109	-106	-102	-95
	$H3$	-110	-113	-130	-128	-131	-123
B67	$H1$	+14.6	+14.6	-33.3	-34.0	+13.2	+13.3
	$H2$	-102	-104	-128	-127	-122	-116
	$H3$	-138	-141	-150	-155	-135	-142

Table Recap of the model to hardware correlation for the three considered layouts using the $EM + Y_{surf-fit}(V)$ approach. All data is expressed in dBm and is taken a +15 dBm of fundamental input power at 900 MHz.

Example of substrate impact:

Next steps: Simulate such substrate impact

Conclusion and Take-Aways

Conclusion

- **Stringent linearity** specification for advanced telecommunications
 - Overall RFIC linearity affected by the substrate
- **Large-signal modelling is a challenge**
 - Account for static and dynamic behaviours of carriers and traps
 - Under non-equilibrium transient RF signal excitations

Dynamic effects and trap/carrier inertia (time constants) were highlighted

The concept of instantaneous substrate impedance out of equilibrium was introduced, accounting for such effects

- **Modelling of arbitrary RF layouts**
 - Combining TCAD transient instantaneous surface impedance descriptions with full EM simulations of linear material regions
 - Promising initial results

Take-Aways

Need for specially optimized/engineered RF substrate solutions

The physical phenomena associated to *Parasitic Surface Conduction* and to trap-rich passivation was reviewed

Large-signal CPW model (2D cross-section coupled with T-line theory) developed in TCAD with good results

Work starting with an EDA company at the end of 2021

Interest of such Modelling:

1. Support the development of future/novel RF substrate solutions
2. Evaluate the linearity impact of the substrate in an RF module during IC design

**Thank you for
your attention**

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Backup Slides

Quantitative Charge Balance

$$Q_{Applied} = Q_{DC} + Q_{ox} - Q_{MS} \quad [C \cdot cm^{-2}] \quad (3.49)$$

$$= V_{DC}C_{ox} + Q_{ox} - V_{MS}C_{ox} \quad [C \cdot cm^{-2}] \quad (3.50)$$

$$Q_{comp} = -Q_{Applied} \quad \text{at equilibrium} \quad [C \cdot cm^{-2}] \quad (3.51)$$

Curves in $[cm^{-3}eV^{-1}]$
 Surfaces in $[cm^{-3}]$
 Volumes in $[cm^{-2}]$

$$Q_{comp} = \int_0^{t_Q} \rho_q dy$$

$$= \int_0^{t_Q} Q_{free} dy + \int_0^{t_Q} Q_{trap} dy$$

$$= \int_0^{t_Q} q \cdot (p - n) dy + \int_0^{t_Q} q \cdot (N_{tD}^+ - N_{tA}^-) dy$$

$$= Q_{freeINT} + Q_{trapINT} \quad [C \cdot cm^{-2}] \quad (3.52)$$

free carriers & ionized traps

Traps for RF performance

HR bulk & $N_{ox} = 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-2}$

Trap densities $g_A(E)$ and $g_D(E)$ are proportional to parameter NT

As NT increases:

- Interface **Fermi level** moves deep.
- **Ionized traps** provide the majority of the compensation charge.
- Substrate impedance ρ_{eff} **increases**.
- Substrate becomes **more linear**.

Traps for RF performance – bias dependency

As NT increases:

- Interface Fermi level becomes **tightly pinned**.
- Small variation in E_F results in large variations in N_{trap} , and little in N_{free} .
- Substrate impedance $\rho_{eff}(N_{free})$ **becomes bias independent**.
- Substrate linearity also.

